

Impact of An Uncertain Political System on The Volatility of The Financial Markets ...

Impact of An Uncertain Political System on The Volatility of The Financial Markets in The Fiscal Year 2021–2022. Evidences From Pakistan

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Abstract

The research aims to calculate the effect of political unpredictability on Pakistan's financial markets over the fiscal years 2021–2022. It also establishes the direction and strength of the association among the “Pakistan Stock Exchange's” political operations and the country's three financial markets—the FOREX market, the interbank market, and the Pakistan Stock Exchange. The OLS model is used to attempt to compute the effects of several forms of political accomplishments on monetary markets after collecting primary data on daily political activity and secondary data on the indicators of the three markets. We discovered through research that these actions have a negative impact on the financial markets under consideration, however the relevance differs for other markets. Numerous additional stochastic activities, many of which have not been considered, along with terrorist actions, are to blame for the poor performance of the financial markets. The report suggests

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changing the money supply and interest rates to create a more favorable climate for investors and institutional growth in the creative, sustainable business.

Keywords: Political Instability; Financial Markets; KSE; KIBOR; FOREX

1. INTRODUCTION

However political unrest has consistently stood in the way of Pakistan's prosperity in general and the success of the stock market in particular. Since gaining independence, Pakistan has been entangled in a web of political unrest and turmoil. The prevalence of crises and the unfavourable economic climate they produce should have legitimate justifications. With the exception of the previous two democratic governments from 2008 to 2013 and 2013 to 2018, After winning a mandate from the people, no political party in Pakistan has completed its entire democratic five-year term. Most of the time when the military takes over, it overthrows the democratically elected government. The nation's economy and stock market have been severely impacted by this political unrest. The financial markets have grown increasingly erratic and sensitive to news of significance. These news items might be related to events that signify changes in the macroeconomic outlook, instability brought on by terrorism, or political turmoil. News disseminates swiftly in today's information-driven environment, and infection may spread quickly. The Pakistan Stock Market has been severely impacted by the terrorism attacks and shifting political landscapes; as a result, Many foreign investors have stopped investing in Pakistani stock exchanges (Sherani, 2014).

Pakistan is strategically situated at the intersection of Iran, China, India, Afghanistan, and the oil-rich Gulf States. The Taliban (Al Qaeda) and the war on terror had a significant negative impact on Pakistan's growth process from 2000 to 2012, as did the country's division on the global political stage. These events discouraged the Pakistan Stock Exchange, but a stable political climate has since encouraged and prospered the nation's stock market, which has twice been named the best-performing stock market in the region. Over the past two decades, both the stock market's capitalization and per-capita income have more than quadrupled. A major impact on the performance of the stock market might result from Pakistan's heightened standing in the fight against terrorism, Pakistan's political threat and its repercussions have, nevertheless, been the focus of intense attention in this age. Investors' expectations regarding the country's business sector's future possibilities have been affected by Pakistan's general situation, which offers a distinctive socioeconomic and political climate (Collier, 2003). The efficient market hypothesis, first out by Fama in 1965, assumes that any information that is made available to the public has an effect on stock prices. It is founded on information systems that clarify the necessary condition for the fairly robust version of the efficient market. All key economic events are covered in this data, all of which have some bearing on the nation's overall economic activity, and all of which might potentially be applied to the corporate context of the enterprises (Ross et al., 2008). Evidence suggests that Pakistan's political environment is characterised by bitter rivalry between political parties and instability brought on by the dictatorial military's frequent interventions. The sentiment and general performance of the business sector are affected by the information that is accessible in such a setting. The "Pakistan Stock Exchange suffered significantly after Benazir

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Bhutto's assassination, as the index dropped by about 5%. (Sohail and Hussain 2009). The Pakistan Stock Exchange, the biggest, most liquid, and one of the first stock exchanges in south Asia, was established on September 18, 1947. On March 10, 1949, it was legally constituted as a company limited by guarantee under the name "Karachi Stock Exchange." Lahore's second stock market opened its doors in October 1970. The Islamabad Stock Exchange was founded in October 1989 to serve the needs of investors in the nation's north. In the end, the Pakistani government consolidated the three exchanges' activities, which became known as the Pakistan Stock Exchange Limited, with effect from January 11, 2016. (PSX) The Karachi Stock Exchange currently has 854 businesses listed, and as of April 28, 2015, it has a market value of Rs. 10.807 billion (KSE). The most well-known measure for measuring market activity is the KSE-100 index. On May 30, 2016, the market's KSE-100 index closing price was 36235 points. The stock market is now moving downward and has experienced a significant decline from a level of more than 36,720 points in February 2016, the level the market reached for the first time ever. The level was reached from a low of 4782 points in December 2021 following the April 2022 stock market meltdown (DAWN, 2022)". This situation shows how volatile Pakistan's stock market is. Due to the significance of the Pakistan Stock Exchange, this study has looked at how political events affect the Pakistan Stock Exchange. There isn't much literature currently written about this kind of practice. Consequently, this work will make a valuable contribution to the relevant literature.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A political system is made up of cooperation between various political factions, and it directly influences stock market performance by developing new regulations and laws. Markets saw significant changes as a consequence of reactions from investors, businesspeople, and the general public that were either in favour of or against the new and current political structure (Bittlingmayer, 1998). The democratic political system has numerous shortcomings, especially in the beginning. It was clear that democratic nations used their resources in a highly inefficient manner, which undermined investor trust and exacerbated stock market volatility (Quinn & Woolley, 2001; Rodrik, 2000). It has been established that between 1987 and 2000, the volatility of the Philippine stock market was exacerbated by the country's regularly shifting political landscape brought on by a number of military coups and FX restrictions (Bautista, 2003). Over time, people came to trust the dominant political system and desired a stable one, whether it was democratic or authoritarian in form. Rapid political system change raised political risk by creating political ambiguity, which exacerbated market volatility in Canada. Additionally, according to Beaulieu, Cosset, and Essaddam (2005) and Pástor & Veronesi (2013), it made investors claim higher risk premiums, which were particularly expensive in developing nations. Equity markets in the MENA area were impacted by political upheaval that was clearly visible in Arab nations (Chau, Deesomsak, & Wang, 2014). (2014) Nazir, Younus, Kaleem, and Anwar investigated how domestic political events affected PSX. Results showed that the political events' nature supports PSX's course.

2. METHODOLOGY

Time series data are used in this piece of research. Over the course of a year, it uses high frequency data, which is everyday data (i.e. from 1st July 2021 to 30th June 2022). Various

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sources have been used to get the data. Three financial markets—banking market, which represents the money market; stock market (KARACHI STOCK EXCHANGE); and forex market, which represents the capital market—have each been studied individually using secondary data. The KSE website's data was used to create the KSE Index. The State Bank of Pakistan's Monetary Policy Department provided the information on foreign exchange, often known as rupee dollar parity. The information on KIBOR (Karachi Inter Bank Offer Rate) was also collected from the State Bank of Pakistan's Domestic Markets & Monetary Management Department (DMMD). The daily gathering of political uncertainty has proven to be the most time-consuming step in the main data collection procedure. Daily details on these events have been gathered from a number of news sources, including "The Daily Dawn." We divide the political unpredictability into four different dummy variables to better understand how it affects Pakistan's financial markets. The political unpredictability has been divided into four groups, P1, P2, P3, and P4. Depending on the level of difficulty, a certain group has been allocated to each exercise. Following is a quick explanation of the dummy variables used in the study:

- P1 is equal to 1 in the event that political or other significant persons have been targeted by political uncertainty, and 0 in the absence of such an occurrence.
- For political unrest to occur in economically significant or financially active cities, P2 is equal to 1; for such unrest not to occur, P2 is equal to 0.
- P3 is equivalent to 1 when important events occur, however in cities without a finance sector,
- In contrast, P4 equals 1 when minor political unrest occurs in small cities and 0 when it does not.
- PST is equal to 1 if there has been a structural change throughout the research period; otherwise, it is equal to 0. We as a nation have grown so much more resilient to such attacks that even though the majority of the activities listed under P4 are not minor in terms of the cost to human lives and the infrastructure of the cities, perhaps as a result of the peaking magnitude of political unrest in the country over the past year or so, that loss of normal citizens' or human beings' lives or the blowing up of the country's resources does not mean much loss to us, neither in a moral sense nor in terms of money.

3. ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES AND RESULTS

E-views, time series econometric software, has been heavily utilized for the estimate of outcomes. The "MULTIPLE REGRESSION MODEL" is the model that is utilized for analysis. This model explains the direction of the interaction between the repressors and the regressands as well as the magnitude of the effect of political uncertainty on the various financial markets. KSEI, FOREX rate, and KIBOR serve as repressors in this study whereas the four types of political uncertainty serve as regressors. The study evaluates how these three markets are affected by political unpredictability. The model's functional form would be as follows:

$$FM = f(P_i) \quad (1)$$

Where;

"FM indicates any type of the above mentioned financial market. P_i indicates dummy variable capturing the impact of any type of the political uncertainty which affects the financial

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markets in Pakistan. To assess the impact, the functional form of the equation no. 1 is converted into mathematical equation, which is as follows”

$$\text{FM} = \alpha + \beta P_i \quad (2)$$

Where;

FM = any financial market operating in Pakistan e.g. KSE, FOREX, Money market.

α = intercept

β = parameter to be estimated or coefficient.

D_i = dummy variables ranging from P1 to P4. While P1, P2, P3 and P4 are already explained.”

The study includes PST as a second dummy variable for KIBOR analysis. It refers to any economic structural changes that may soon have an effect on the interbank market.

We need to transform equation (2) into an econometric equation since the dependent variable (financial markets) is also influenced by several additional factors known as stochastic or error terms.

$$\text{FM} = \alpha + \beta P_i + e_i \quad (3)$$

where the error word is e_i .

Because the dynamics of various financial markets vary somewhat. For estimating purposes, we must estimate the findings independently using a different equation. Below are some of these:

I. STOCK MARKET

We initially examine the effects of four dummy variables on the KSE 100 index since the KSE is the most active or efficient of all the financial markets in Pakistan. We transform the daily values of the KSE 100 Index into their log values in order to specifically study the growth of the KSE Index. We use the natural log of equation (2) to smooth the KSE Index because the stock market has experienced a lot of volatility over the past year.

$$\text{KSEI} = \alpha + \beta P_i + e_i \quad (4)$$

Taking natural log on the left hand side we get;

$$\text{Ln}(\text{KSEI}) = \alpha + \beta P_i + e_i \quad (5)$$

This is the last equation that may be used to estimate how political uncertainty will affect the KSE.

The Karachi Stock Exchange 100 Index's natural log is a function of the P_i , with P1, P2, P3, and P4 standing in for the various kinds and degrees of political unpredictability, according to the equation. We observe a negative impact of P1, P2, and P4 on the LnKSEI after independently regressing each of the dummy variables (P1 to P4) on the LnKSEI. It's significant to notice that P1 and P2's separate effects appeared to be muted. Therefore, we combine the two variables and give them the label P1' in order to improve the overall impact of P1 and P2. Therefore, P3 and P4 stay the same but the political unpredictability affecting important persons and significant financial sectors is collectively referred to as "big events" (grouped in P1').

“By applying OLS regression technique, we estimate the following equation;- $\text{Ln}(\text{KSEI}) = \alpha + \beta P1' + \gamma D4 + e_i \quad (6)$

Where; $\text{Ln}(\text{KSEI})$ = natural log Karachi Stock Exchange Index. P1' = political uncertainty targeting key personnel and major financial cities. P4 = minor activities in small cities. α, β, γ

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= parameters to be estimated. e_i = stochastic/ error/residual term."

The findings clearly show that our model is the best match, with an R2 value of 0.98 or 98%. It suggests that the independent variable accounts for 98% of the variability in the dependent variable (LnKSEI). Walter Watson Statistics similar to 1.96, which is closer to 2, demonstrates that the autocorrelation problem is not a major obstacle for the regression model. We reject the null hypothesis (i.e. $H_0: \beta = 0$) since the standard error of the model is likewise quite modest (0.016336) and increases the computed value of t-statistics. The F-statistics, which show how significant and well-fit the model is overall, are 14379.05, which is comparably quite high. The intercept, shown by C or, is the weighted average of all the factors that were disregarded but may have affected the KSE index. Its value is 9.441305, and at the 1% level of significance, it is significant (highly significant). Our shows that a range of events that were excluded from this research owing to time constraints have an impact on KSEI. The test may most likely incorporate variables like capital taxes on stock dividend income, capital inflows, future business plans of businesses listed on the stock market, and external shocks. Similar to this, KSE is negatively impacted by terrorist activity. Particularly, the P1 dummy variable's value (beta = -0.005021 at 2% level of significance) suggests that a 1% rise in the pertinent political unpredictability may have a 0.5% negative impact on the KSE 100 Index. This indicates that the political unrest affecting important financial centres and those targeting important national figures has a negative and considerable influence on the KSE's performance. To put it another way, if there is any political unrest in the area, the KSE 100 Index may fall. The KSE 100 Index has also been significantly impacted by the dummy variable P4. It shows that modest political unrest in small cities has a negative influence on the KSE 100 Index but is not very substantial. In this case, the projected negative value of Y (-0.000137) means to back up the claim that even a tiny amount of political unpredictability has a detrimental effect on the KSE. More accurately, the aforementioned political unpredictability included in P4 together with other lingering variables also have a detrimental impact on how the KSEI operates. The crucial paradigm change in policy measures may have a substantial influence on how these activities affect KSE performance. The degree of political unpredictability in an area has a significant impact on government policies and those of other relevant organisations. The economic climate would be more unpredictable the more political instability there was, which would also increase the rate at which policy measures changed. Since Karachi serves as the hub of the nation's financial activity and the Karachi Stock Exchange is the largest stock exchange in the nation, the city's susceptibility to political unpredictability is likely to lead to volatility in the economy's liquidity. The possibility of a negative impact on the financial markets, especially the KSE, would increase with the city's political unpredictability. As a result, there would be an increase in capital flight, a decline in investments, a decline in exports, and a depletion of foreign exchange reserves.

II. FOREX MARKET

The marketplace where a country's money is exchanged for other currencies is known as the foreign exchange market. The average daily rate of a currency is based on the daily buying and selling of that currency. The daily average FOREX rate is determined by the equilibrium

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point of the demand and supply of a currency, which occurs concurrently on the local and foreign markets. Any foreign currency can be used to calculate the rate. Brokers are often used to convert currencies, although a wide range of organisations, including individuals, commercial banks, investment banks, brokerage firms, clearing houses, and foreign exchange markets as a whole, are also involved in the process.

The FOREX market is the largest financial market in the world, but it ranks second in terms of Pakistan. Since the foreign exchange rate may be stated in two different ways, i.e., directly and indirectly.

We utilized a straight quote of the Pakistani rupee in this investigation (PKR). We use I/PKR to represent the exchange rate of the Pakistani rupee in terms of the US dollar (direct quotation). By taking its natural log, the exchange rate's volatility is decreased. We must assess how political unpredictability affects the stability of exchange rates or how much the highlighted actions devalue the native currency relative to other currencies in our research (U.S. Dollar).

"We have derived the following equation: $\ln(ER) = \alpha + \beta P_i + e_i$ (7)

Where;

ER = exchange rate. While for analysis purpose we use the following equation. $\ln(ER) = \alpha + \beta_1(P_1) + \beta_2(P_2) + \gamma(P_4) + e_i$ (8)

where;

$\ln(ER)$ = natural log of exchange rate, P_1 = political uncertainty targeting the key personalities P_2 = political uncertainty taking place in the major financial cities. P_4 = minor political uncertainty in small cities. α, β, γ = parameters to be estimated e_i = residual/ error term.

Equation (8) makes it evident that the political unpredictability gathered in P_1 and P_2 has an impact on ER. We use the OLS approach to regress the provided econometric equation in order to obtain the empirical results."

The obtained findings indicate that the explanatory factors account for 99% of the changes in the dependent variable (ER), with an R^2 value of 0.99 or 99%. The model is a best fit since the R^2 value is rather high. The autocorrelation problem in the regression model is not present, as indicated by the Durbin-Watson statistic of 2, which is equal to 2. The overall relevance of the model is demonstrated by the very high and substantial F- statistics value. The regression's very small standard error results in a high t statistic. The intercept factor, C or, is highly significant at Alpha -4.078457 and shows that the variables that were disregarded led to the depreciation of the Pakistani rupee in relation to the US dollar. The effect of dummy variable P_1 is negative but inconsequential. Therefore, we may infer that, while the political unpredictability known as P_1 does have a negative influence on the exchange rate of the Pakistani rupee, the effect is hardly noticeable. The coefficient of P_2 , which is similarly very modest, shows that the FOREX market's response to underlying activity is almost nonexistent. It concludes that P_2 activities have a detrimental and negligible influence on how the FOREX rate is calculated. P_4 activities' influence on FOREX is evaluated similarly to P_1 and P_2 activities.

We may deduce that there is a negative correlation between political unpredictability and the FOREX rate based on all of the aforementioned coefficient values. The negative sign suggests

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that any such event is to blame for the local currency's decline relative to foreign currencies (U.S. Dollar in the present case). There may be a number of reasons for this hidden association, even though the impact on Pakistan is not particularly obvious. Due to the strong resiliency of the financial markets of Pakistan, the effect might not be felt there. It is clear from the daily statistics on political unpredictability that these occurrences occurred a lot during the study period. These activities range in severity from mildly offensive events to extremely serious terrorist efforts that terrify the whole human race. It is plausible to anticipate the convergence of financial markets in this situation. The impact must be negative since such events create economic uncertainty, raise risks and liquidity shortages, decrease exports, devalue currencies, diminish domestic and international investments, and consequently result in a capital flight from the economy. However, in the case of Pakistan, the great frequency of such events may be to blame for the nation's overall icy demeanour, and those engaged in currency trading or any other financial sector may take these incidents for granted. This explains why the range in PKR depreciation is far lower than perceived expectations. Therefore, we can confidently state that political instability does not necessarily indicate its influence on Pakistan's foreign currency market, unless the incident is particularly unfavorable or garners international attention, such as the killing of the country's former prime minister, Benazir Bhutto.

III. KIBOR

The Karachi Inter Bank Offer Rate (KIBOR) is the average of commercial banks' daily offer rates. It is the typical daily rate that a bank charges other commercial banks for short-term borrowing. In other words, KIBOR serves as a benchmark to assess a nation's banking sector's capacity to handle short-term loans and funding. The highlighted actions could also have an impact on KIBOR rates.

Since it reflects the commercial banks' capacity to borrow money, the interbank rate is a relative indication of the performance and efficiency of the banking sector.

Econometric equation for KIBOR is given as;

"KIBOR = $\alpha + \beta P_i + e_i$ (9). To find out the empirical results of impact of political uncertainty on banking industry (KIBOR) we estimate the following econometric equation by OLS technique.

$$\text{KIBOR} = \alpha + \beta D1 + \gamma \text{PST} + e_i \quad (10)$$

Where;

KIBOR = Karachi Inter Bank Offer Rate, P1 = major political uncertainty targeting key personalities. PST = dummy variable for structural changes. α , β , γ = parameters to be estimated e_i = stochastic/error/residual term."

The following conclusions on the influence of political uncertainty on the money market or interbank market are obtained by using the OLS method to equation no (KIBOR). The data revealed that the R2 value was 0.98, or 98%, indicating that the model was the best match. The fluctuations in the explanatory (independent) variable account for 98% of the variations in the dependent variable, KIBOR. The results are not plagued by the threat of the autocorrelation problem, according to the estimated value of Durbin Watson Statistics, which is 1.95. This demonstrates the reliability of the findings since they may be applied to the

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creation of KIBOR-related policies. Because the standard errors are so tiny, the t-statistics are greater. Again, very high F-statistic values, 15109.34, demonstrate the model's overall relevance. At the 1% level of significance, the value of the intercept, C or, alpha is 8.474, which is high and significant. It is an indication that other variables are more likely to be the cause of the bank rate hike. The coefficient of P1, or 1, has a value of Beta is 0.001382. Political instability in P1 does have a small but favourable impact on the KIBOR. Positive indications suggest that the interbank rate will increase the more often the activities occur. Additionally positive and very significant at the 1% level of significance is the coefficient of P2. It suggests that a variety of factors, not just political unpredictability, are important in affecting variations in the KIBOR rate. Compared to the stock market, KIBOR is more heavily impacted by political uncertainties (KSE). This is due to the fact that banks have a nationwide branch network, but KSE is limited to a single location. Therefore, it is more likely that political uncertainty will have an impact on the financial sector. The KIBOR rate shows the greater influence in its form.

FINDINGS AND COMMENDATIONS

The primary objective of this study was to ascertain the impact that various forms of political unpredictability will have on the three financial markets in Karachi, Pakistan: the stock market, the foreign exchange market, and the money market. The OLS regression model may lead to the following conclusions:

- The current political unrest has had a negative impact on Pakistan's economy. The performance of KSE has been negatively and considerably impacted by the political unpredictability in Pakistan. Additionally, compared to other markets, the political unpredictability has had a considerably greater impact on the KSE. This could be because the KSEI is more responsive to events than to economic fundamentals due to its variable character.
- Political unpredictability has a small but negative impact on the FOREX market. The interbank data utilised in the investigation may be a factor in the political unpredictability's little effect on FOREX rates. Therefore, any volatility brought on by such occurrences may be reduced as long as the SBP continues to actively intervene in the FOREX market.
- The influence on the KIBOR rate is a very beneficial development since it is seen to be a good indicator of the short-term loans that banks offer, even if it is assessed to be negative and minor. If political uncertainty has a large negative influence on KIBOR, it may have a bad effect on the nation's investment plans, which might have had a negative effect on Pakistan's economy.
- The majority of the study's findings are consistent with the predictions made by theory. The KSE 100 Index and KIBOR rate outcome estimations are in line with forecasts. Although appropriately guided, the econometric results for the second regression do not fully support the hypothesis as predicted.
- It is unquestionably harmful for the economy and financial markets when terrorism is on the rise in a nation.
- Last but not least, the political uncertainty's aims have a significant influence on how the financial markets are affected. The study may have a number of flaws, which are primarily attributable to time restrictions. Following are some of the policy recommendations that

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might be made in light of the current study;

- Because of political unpredictability, the government and state should concentrate on institutional development in light of the study's empirical results and conclusions. Under the auspices of this organisation, an anti-political uncertainty framework of global relevance will be developed, improved, and made accessible to the public. Before such such disaster occurs, the general public should be warned in advance, and rehabilitation should be a priority right away.

- In addition to the welfare of the general populace, the anti-political uncertainty-creating institution must include adequate contingency planning to reduce the financial risk faced by financial institutions and the whole economy.

- Since this study's econometric analysis demonstrated that political uncertainty has a negative influence on financial markets, economic policy should play a significant role in efforts to reduce political uncertainty. To stop the tsunami of disruption caused in any of the aforementioned financial markets, effective solutions must be developed. The main domestic and foreign investors withdraw their money from the financial markets as a result of the ongoing terrorist attacks on the economy, like in Pakistan. Capital is leaving the economy, which has a negative impact on the local currency. Policies including expanding the money supply and decreasing interest rates must be implemented in order to boost investor confidence and maintain the accumulation of foreign reserves in order to reduce the danger of currency depreciation.

- In order to make the economy more resilient to shocks and to improve its financial foundation, policy must be created. Opportunities for domestic manufacturers will be emphasised in order to boost exports and subsequently domestic currency demand. This is a crucial step in preventing currency depreciation, and it will also reduce the likelihood of a trade imbalance. This has significant money market policy implications. Investment in research and development and innovative security measures is also need of the day.

- Lastly, policies need to be developed and expanded globally to improve coordination and collaboration among the key players in the world's financial markets. In order to provide financial assistance during the critical financial crisis that follows any significant act of political instability, policies promoting cordial connections among the central banks of international significance should also be supported. Based on its findings, the research primarily advises that while establishing policies for the three different types of financial markets, the concerned policy makers should consider the influence of political instability. However, the effect of terrorism differs on each market depending on its severity, location, etc.

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